

Factors Associated with Early Dental Implant Failure

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays dental implant is considered to be as an effective treatment modality for replacing missing teeth in fully and partially edentulous patients. However, this type of treatment is not always successful but in some cases it results in implant failure. Risk factors associated with dental implant failure is a significant concern for both dentist and patient. Dental implant failures divided into an early, and late implant failures. When osseointegration fails to occur it means that it is an early implant failure (before prosthetic restoration), and late implant failure (after prosthetic restoration), occur when the achieved osseointegration is lost after a period of function.

The aim of this concise review is to provide a general information to dentist about the most common risk factors contributing to early dental implant failure.

Keywords: Dental Implants, Early dental implant failure, Risk factors.

INTRODUCTION

Implants have become the treatment of choice, when missing teeth require replacement. Dental implant reconstruction is a very successful treatment modality that can be offered to our patients with missing or failing teeth. Like with any medical, surgical, or dental treatment there are always risks and no procedure is foolproof. Implant failures, can be classified into; 1- Biological failures may occur due to the inadequacy of the host tissue to establish or maintain osseointegration, 2- Mechanical failures may occur due to fracture of implants, connecting screws, bridge frameworks, coatings, etc., 3- Iatrogenic failures may occur due to nerve damages, wrong alignment of implants, etc., 4- Inadequate or insufficient patient adaptation may occur due to psychological, aesthetic, and phonetic problems. Biological implant failures can be further classified as early failure and late failure (1).

Implant failure can occur due to a wide variety of reasons including quantity and quality of bone, advanced age, the dentist's experience, location of implant placement, length of the implant, axial loading, and oral hygiene maintenance, chronic periodontitis, systemic diseases, heavy smoking, implant location, an inadequate number of implants,

para-functional habits, and inappropriate prosthesis design (2).

Osseointegration:

One of the first definitions of osseointegration is “a direct functional and structural connection between living bone and the surface of a load-bearing implant”. According to the Dorland Illustrated Dictionary, osseointegration is the direct anchorage of an implant by the formation of bony tissue around the implants without the growth of fibrous tissue at the bone-implant (1). Progressive peri-implant bone loss together with a soft tissue inflammatory lesion can be defined as peri-implantitis, and is considered to be a major cause of failure after osseointegration(3) . Dental implant failure defined as the first instance at which the performance of the implant, measured in some quantitative way, falls below a specified, acceptable level (1).

Ailing and failing implants:

Implant with bone loss and pocketing is defined as ailing implant but static at the maintenance checks, it is not mobile and usually is associated with signs of peri-implantitis. Failing implant exhibit bone loss with pocketing, bleeding upon probing, purulence, and evidence of continuing bone

loss irrespective of therapy, therefore, an implant that is progressively losing its bone anchorage, but is still clinically stable, can be defined as failing .

Ailing and failing implants are amenable to therapy. If an implant manifests mobility, it means that it has failed and needs to be removed (4).

The most common causes of implant failure at an early stage after implant placement are operator experience, excessive surgical trauma, bacterial contamination, premature overloading with micromotion, and some local as well as systemic characteristics of the host. Excessive occlusal stress in conjunction with host characteristics peri-implantitis are believed to be etiologic factors for late losses (5). Most implant failures have been reported to occur in the maxilla, with almost three times as many implant losses as in the mandible (6).

Dental implant failures can be prevented with proper patient selection, excellent surgical technique, placing an adequate restoration on the implant, educating the patient to maintain meticulous oral hygiene and evaluating the implant both clinically and radiographically at frequent recall visits (4).

Diagnostic parameters in the early recognition of implant failure:

Common signs for failure are implant mobility, infection and marginal bone loss. Diagnostic techniques, such as probing pocket depth, radiographic tools, and microbial sampling are used during the maintenance phase of the dental implant for early recognition of dental implant failures (7).

Early detection and treatment of early progressive bone loss around dental implants are the key for saving early failing implants. Reevaluation visits of 4–6 weeks post-implant placement are carried out to detect any signs of early failure, so that immediate treatment can be undertaken if needed (8).The decision to remove an implant needs to be based on clinical assessments and radiographic evaluations or both. If any implant is deemed hopeless, there are devices that facilitate its removal. Furthermore, re-implantations can be performed successfully, but their survival rate would be lower than that of implants placed at sites from which they were not lost formerly (9).

Risk factors associated with early dental implant failure:

The fact that implants are not successful in a small percentage of cases, challenges dental researchers and clinicians to study risks associated with failures. Implant failure can be generally divided into patient-related factors (*e.g.*, general patient health status, smoking habits, quantity and quality of bone, oral hygiene maintenance, etc.), implant characteristics (*e.g.*, dimensions, coating, loading, etc.) (2).

Bone quality:

The primary predictor of implant failure is the poor bone quality, where type 4 and 1 bones are more likely to fail (10). The cortical and cancellous ratio of local bone is extremely important for implant stability at the time of surgery and determining the local bone condition is critical for treatment success (11). Clinicians should be aware of the increased risk of early implant failure in the presence of implant-supported maxillary rehabilitation. The reason for this may be that jawbone quality and quantity are often more compromised in maxillary than in mandibular sites (12). Furthermore, short-term evidence suggests that high rates of implant success can be achieved in maxillary

sites, even those with low trabecular density, if an adequate volume of bone exists to accommodate the implants. Although the rate of crestal bone resorption around oral implants is usually low and may not be site-specific (11).

Implant design and location

The smooth surfaces of implant will not provide adequate biomechanical coupling with the bone surrounding the implant neck, in that the stress range induced by a polished surface is limited. The surface texture of threaded, plasma-coated or sandblasted implants generates a heterogeneous stress field around an implant in function, such a stress field are conducive to bone formation (13).

It has been reported that increasing implant length will affect the success rates up to a limit, possibly because the increased length of the bone implant interfacial contact will increase the potential for greater mechanical resistance to masticatory forces. While other studies report that implant length does not significantly affect survival rates (14). It is not recommended to use a short implant, it has a high failure rates, because it is believed that occlusal forces must be dissipated over a

large implant area in order for the bone to be preserved (15).

Recently short implants can be placed successfully in atrophic regions of the jaws with similar long-term prognoses as standard dental implants with a reasonable prosthetic design. Using short implants could be a preferable choice. Short implants can be placed, even when the residual bone height over the mandibular canal is 5–7 mm, without the need for vertical bone augmentation (16&17).

It has been reported that, implant site was not a significant factor in implant failure, they also found that more failures occur in the posterior region of both jaws compared to the anterior mandibular region (1).

Regarding immediate loading of dental implant, it should be postponed at least 2 months after insertion, and excessive force and occlusal loading during initial phase of healing should be avoided. However immediate loading of dental implant is not a serious risk for implant stability or osseointegration and survival rate of dental implants. Unsuitable design and inappropriate prosthetic constructions are potential risk factors for dental implant failure. Para-functional habits (i.e. bruxism, clenching and grinding) are two responsible

factors for peri-implantitis and dental implant failure. Bruxism causes occlusal overload on implant and consequently alveolar bone loss around dental implant (18).

Placement of dental implant in a sites with infection such as; (presence of pathology at implant site, placement of implant in an infected tooth socket, placement of implant adjacent to undiagnosed endodontically involved tooth, adjacent to an existing lesion, such a cyst and in the presence of periodontitis), may lead to implant failure(2).

The systemic factors that affect dental implant failure

Most of the systemic factors that affect dental implant failure are; aging, osteoporosis, corticosteroid therapy, diabetes mellitus, immune deficiency, bleeding disorder, neuropsychiatric disorders, patients with history of head and neck cancer, cardiovascular disease, alcoholism and smoking habit, mucocutaneous diseases, scleroderma and hypothyroidism. It has been reported that osteoporosis, Crohn's disease, and diabetes I, radical hysterectomy, the intake of antidepressants and smoking habits, were all significantly associated with early implant failures (19). Dental implant failure increase in diabetic patients. Patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus tend to have more

failures than non-diabetic ones. No absolute contraindication for implant placement in diabetic patient, because of successful rates of osseointegrated implants in controlled diabetic patients. There is so far no conclusive evidences to include osteoporosis among the risk factors for osseointegrated dental implants. Patients with osteoporosis could be successfully treated using osseointegrated implants (20).

The age

Although there is no scientific evidence to improve differences in osseointegration between young and old patients (20). However it seems that the advanced age was seen to be a possible contributing factor to implant failure (21). It is advised that age should not be used as a reason to exclude patients from being treated with endosseous oral implants (22).

Smoking

Smoking can increase the incidence of peri-implantitis and adversely affects the success of bone grafts. The failure rate of implants placed in grafted maxillary sinuses of smokers is more than twice that seen in nonsmokers (12) and (23). Smokers should be advised to follow the smoking cessation

protocol; complete cessation of smoking for one week before implant placement, to allow reversal of the increased levels of the platelet adhesion and blood viscosity, as well as the shorter-term effects associated with nicotine, and eight weeks after initial implant placement surgery, by which time bone healing phases would have progressed to the osteoblastic phase and early osseointegration would have been established (23).

Radiation:

It worth's wise to note that, there is no absolute contraindication for placing dental implant in radiated jaw especially in the mandible, but healing time after radiation is important (2). The implant therapy should be performed at least one year after irradiation to promote revascularization and partial recuperation of tissues (20).

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that the failure of dental implants may be influenced by many factors. Few absolute contraindications for dental implant therapy can be seen. It seems to be that the most important causes of implant failure can include bone type, presence of infection at the site of implant, implant placement in a radiated jaw as well as heavy smoking. From the other hand roper patient

selection, considering patients local and systemic status, and accurate diagnostic tool can help to decrease the incidence of dental implant failure

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